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Music for Children: Comparing Selections of *Carmina Burana* With Orff Schulwerk

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the musical qualities of Orff Schulwerk were compared with two movements of Carmina Burana that include a children's choir—Amor volat undique and Tempus est iocundum. The author examines the commonalities in elemental forms, contrasting timbres and dynamics, elemental music, modal melodies, and instrumentation between the two. The article shows that Orff's early work in the Güntherschule possibly influenced his compositional techniques in Carmina Burana, and that his ideas continued to unfold as he developed the Schulwerk for children, particularly in the Music for Children volumes.

By Martina Vasil

To music educators, Carl Orff is renowned for his child-centered approach to music and movement education. To those outside of the field of music education, he is best known for his monumental cantata, *Carmina Burana* (Goodkin, 2004; Stein, 1977). Orff was developing the Schulwerk with his adult students at the Güntherschule concurrent to the premiere of *Carmina Burana* in 1937 (Landis & Carder, 1990). He later adapted the Schulwerk for children and published his work in five volumes, *Music for Children* (1950-1954) (Landis & Carder, 1990). What are the similarities between Orff Schulwerk and *Carmina Burana*? Are there similar musical qualities between the *Music for Children* volumes and the movements of *Carmina Burana* that include children's voices—*Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum*? This study will first discuss the historical context of the Schulwerk and *Carmina Burana*, and then will delve into the questions posed.

Historical Context

Orff Schulwerk

The groundwork for Orff Schulwerk began with Orff's travels in Europe in the 1920s. Orff was surprised at the lack of rhythmic awareness he observed in highly trained singers, actors, dancers, and musicians, and he developed an interest in movement training to remedy this problem (Orff, 1963). He sought to create a new way of teaching music that differed from the typical conservatory style of music education (Landis & Carder, 1990) and was drawn to those leading the modern dance movement: Emile Jaques-Dalcroze, Mary Wigman, and Rudolf von Laban (Orff, 1963).

In 1924, Orff collaborated with German artist and writer Dorothee Günther to open the Güntherschule in Munich. The school focused on the combined study of music, gymnastics, and dance, incorporating ideas from Dalcroze, Laban, and Mensendieck (corrective and preventative physical exercises) (Goodkin, 2004; Landis & Carder, 1990), and provided Orff with many opportunities to experiment and develop his ideas for music education (Orff, 1963).

From 1924 to 1944, while at the Güntherschule, Orff departed from the traditional use of piano accompaniment in dance training and, instead, asked his students to accompany themselves with nonpitched percussion instruments, such as rattles, drums, and tambourines, as they danced. He also wanted to add melodic elements to the training, and worked with piano and harpsichord manufacturer Karl Maendler to create instruments now common in the Orff instrumentarium. Additionally, he worked with Curt Sachs, the curator of the Berlin collection of ancient instruments, to include the recorder (Orff, 1963). Gunild Keetman, Orff's former student at the Güntherschule, was responsible for working out the technique of the recorder as well as determining ways to integrate it into lessons (Goodkin, 2004).

The Schulwerk slowly developed into active, group-participatory activities that engaged adults in the elements of music (Landis & Carder, 1990). Music was newly composed or arranged from folk music. In his approach, Orff emphasized memorization and aural skills over reading notation, although he did see the need for notational literacy once students experienced the musical elements and understood them (Orff, 1963). This period of development and experimentation eventually led to publication of the first edition of the Schulwerk that preserved the music

created at the Güntherschule, *Rhythmic and Melodic Exercises* (1930) (Landis & Carder, 1990).

The Güntherschule was bombed and destroyed in 1944, but old recordings of the music created there were preserved. A few years later Orff was invited to recreate the Güntherschule music with children, as part of a recorded series of educational broadcasts for Bavarian Radio (Landis & Carder, 1990). Orff had scored works only for adults and had to adapt the Schulwerk for children, whose music education he believed should begin with simple concepts and songs suitable for them (Landis & Carder, 1990). Keetman further helped Orff develop materials, and she became an essential figure in the evolution of the Schulwerk (Orff, 1963).

After five years of broadcasting on Bavarian Radio, Orff and Keetman published five volumes of the music they composed from 1950 to 1954, *Music for Children* (Orff, 1963). The volumes included an element that had been missing from the first published version of the Schulwerk—speech. Orff Schulwerk now connected movement, dance, and speech. With these publications, Orff's vision for music and movement education became widespread.

Carmina Burana

Germany was under the control of Adolf Hitler and his National Socialist German Workers' Party (Nazi Party) in the 1930s (Caplan, 1998). The Nazi Party controlled how music was to be composed in Germany, and supported all forms of Germanic folk music and art. German composers were expected to draw upon native folk songs and military/brass music to create their own high-art tradition. Opera became the most highly accepted art form because it embodied storylines and morals that propagated Nazi Party principles (Meyer, 1977).

For the most part, Orff composed in his own style—his compositions partially fit within the guidelines of the Nazi Party (Meyer, 1977). *Carmina Burana* was well received by the audience at its premiere in 1937, but the official Nazi newspaper described the piece as a “mistaken return to primitive elements” and having too much emphasis on “jazzlike rhythmic formulas” (Kowalke, 2000, p. 70). Only after Orff's adaptation of Monteverdi's *Orfeo* premiered successfully in 1940 did the Nazi Party endorse *Carmina Burana*, referring to it as “the clear, ardent, and disciplined music required for our times” (Kowalke, 2000, p. 70).

Figure 1. *Amor volat undique* Flute Melody (A), mm. 5-8.

Figure 2. *Amor volat undique* Children's Melody (B), m. 13, m. 18, m. 23, and m. 24.

Figure 3. *Amor volat undique* Solo Soprano Melody (C), mm. 33-35, mm 38-40, mm. 43-45, and mm. 47-50.

Figure 4. *Amor volat undique* Flute Motif (D).

SCORE AND PARTS TRANSCRIBED FROM *CARMINA BURANA*, (ORFF C., 1956) BY MARTINA VASIL.

Analysis

Two movements of *Carmina Burana* include a children's choir: *Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum*. This analysis will discuss the parallels between the music composed for children's voices in *Carmina Burana* and the Schulwerk, particularly the *Music for Children* volumes. Specifically, elemental forms, contrasting timbres and dynamics, elemental music, modal melodies, and use of instrumentation are examined.

Elemental Forms

The Schulwerk uses simple compositional forms. Favored forms are: AB, ABA, AABA, and rondo. Introductions and/or codas often frame compositions. Repeated interludes and rhythmic or melodic motifs are also common. Similarly, *Amor volat undique* includes a simple melodic flute motif, two introductions, and a repetitive formal structure. The form consists of three melodies—a flute melody (A), a children's melody (B), and a solo soprano melody (C)—and a five-note flute motif (D) (see Figures 1-4). The form is: Intro 1 AAB AB AB'A Intro 2 DC DC DC' C" AAB AB.

Orff framed the first and second half of this movement with introductions. The beginning and end of this movement are similar (AAB AB), with a contrasting middle (DC DC DC' C"). The larger structure can be considered a basic ABA form.

Figure 5. *Tempus est iocundum* Melody A, mm. 23-28.

Figure 6. *Tempus est iocundum* Melody B, mm. 1-4.

SCORE AND PARTS TRANSCRIBED FROM *CARMINA BURANA*, (ORFF C., 1956) BY MARTINA VASIL.

Two main melodies shape the elemental form of *Tempus est iocundum*. One melody is at different times by a solo baritone, solo soprano, children's choir, and the entire vocal ensemble (A) (see Figure 5). The entire vocal ensemble sings a harmonized second melody (B) (see Figure 6). The movement is an AAB form repeated five times.

Contrasting Timbres and Dynamics

Orff Schulwerk often uses contrasting timbres and dynamics to highlight elemental forms. Both timbral shifts and dynamics highlight the AAB form of *Tempus est iocundum*. The repetitive form of this piece allowed Orff to play with multiple vocal timbres and dynamic contrasts. Different combinations of voices sing Melody A each time it is introduced. Each statement of Melody B progresses through three dynamics within three measures: *forte*, *piano*, and *mezzo forte*. This movement exemplifies how Orff used timbre and dynamics to define a large movement.

Elemental Music

Orff's writing for children's voices in *Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum* parallel his beliefs about elemental music. Orff believed children could successfully create satisfying music by taking a simple musical idea, repeating it, and then building upon it (Landis & Carder, 1990). In *Amor volat undique*, the children's choir sings a melodic motif (A D A B^b A G A) in measure 13 that is repeated in measures 18 and 23 and built upon in measure 24 (see Figure 2, page 34). The children's part

also includes a rhythmic motif of six eighth-notes and one quarter-note in measure 13. This motif is repeated in measures 18 and 23 and extended into measure 24 (see Figure 2, page 34).

In *Tempus est iocundum*, the children sing the melodic motif E F# E in measure 23, and the motif is built upon in various ways in measures 24-25 (see Figure 5). The extended motif in measure 25 (E G G F#) is repeated twice within the same measure and is partially repeated and extended in measure 27 (E F# F# E E G G F# E) (see Figure 5). The rhythmic motif for Melody A begins in measure 24 with four eighth-notes and a half-note. The motif is extended to eight eighth-notes in measure 25. The original motif is repeated in measure 26, and the extended motif is repeated in measure 27 (see Figure 5).

Modal Melodies

Orff structured the Schulwerk so that modal music was an extension of pentatonic melodies. Children typically compose within the pentatonic scales first, which limits them to five pitches with no semi-tones. Once students are comfortable improvising within pentatonic scales, the modes (e.g., Dorian, Phrygian, Aeolian) and tonic-subdominant-dominant harmonies are gradually introduced as compositional frameworks. Orff often used short segments (three to five notes) from these modes before introducing the entire seven-note mode or diatonic scale.

Orff used modal melodies in *Carmina Burana*. In *Amor volat undique*, the children sing a five-note melody a cappella, and several factors suggest their

melody is in D Aeolian (D E F G A B^b C D). In the measures before and after the children sing, the note D is played in the bass. The children's melody includes the notes G A B^b C D, but centers on the note A. The flatted third (F), sixth (B^b), and seventh (C), and the strong presence of D and A, suggest D Aeolian tonality (see Figure 2, page 34).

In *Tempus est iocundum*, the children sing a five-note melody that is harmonized with a melodic ostinato (A to E) in the bass and the notes G B D E. The children's melody includes the notes B C# D E F# and centers on E. The flatted seventh (G) and the A and E in the bass suggest that the children's melody is set in A Mixolydian (A B C# D E F# G A) (see Figure 5, page 35).

When writing for children's voices, Orff often kept the parts in unison and selected a small vocal range. This idea is exemplified in the children's melodies in *Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum* as they sing both in unison and both are five-note melodies set within a larger modal scale.

Instrumentation

Tempus est iocundum is orchestrated with many nonpitched percussion instruments that are also prevalent in Orff Schulwerk. Orff sought to use instruments, such as nonpitched percussion, that students could hold and play as they moved through space. He also employed the timpani for dramatic effect, even though it is pitched percussion. This movement includes cymbals, castanets, tambourine, side drum, bass drum, crash cymbals, and timpani.

Conclusion

The similarities between Orff Schulwerk and *Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum* are clear. Elemental forms, contrasting timbres and dynamics,

elemental music, modal melodies, and nonpitched percussion instruments and timpani feature predominantly in the *Music for Children* volumes. Both *Amor volat undique* and *Tempus est iocundum* are composed of elemental forms, with contrasting timbres and dynamics shaping the form of the latter. Orff's writing for children's voices in *Carmina Burana* reflects the elemental processes of Orff Schulwerk. Further, the use of modal melodies highlights the pedagogical processes he used to transition from pentatonic to modal improvisation and composition. The small vocal range and unison singing also reflect the Schulwerk's vocal parts for children. Scholars have noted the predominant use of percussion instruments that Orff scored not only for *Tempus est iocundum*, but also for *Carmina Burana* as a whole: timpani, side drums, bass drum, bells, triangle, cymbals of various kinds, gongs, sleigh bells, three glockenspiels, xylophone, castanets, ratchet, celesta, and two pianos (Stein, 1977). Nonpitched percussion, glockenspiels, xylophones, and timpani feature predominantly in the *Music for Children* volumes. Last, *Carmina Burana* combines music, movement, and speech—core elements of Orff Schulwerk (Landis & Carder, 1990).

Orff composed *Carmina Burana* and worked on the Schulwerk concurrently. It is noteworthy that the cantata was described as elemental and rhythmic, because these became important characteristics of the Schulwerk as it was developed for children. It is possible that Orff's early work in the Güntherschule influenced his compositional process when creating the cantata, and that this thought process continued as he developed *Music for Children*. The cantata reflects qualities of Orff's elemental approach to music education and shows that music for children can be high art. ■

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